

Transparent and computer-assisted integration of NAM results in decision-making considering uncertainty

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Abstract

In the search for alternatives to replace in vivo methods, the application of assessment frameworks involving New Approach Methodologies (NAMs) often leads to the simultaneous availability of multiple pieces of evidence of different quality. When integrated into defined data structures, combinations of NAMs can generate answers to complex toxicological questions. However, if they are not integrated correctly, a collection of NAM results may produce misleading results that complicate the assessment process or lead to wrong conclusions.

This talk will focus on understanding this challenge and exploring ways to overcome it. Specifically, it will illustrate how the integration of mathematical frameworks into computational tools can provide simple, user-friendly solutions for data management and transparent decision-making. The discussion will focus on cases where multiple NAMs are applied to address the same toxicological question and will include a demonstration of a software tool developed to tackle this issue.